

PrAEctiCe

Potentials of Agroecological practices in East Africa
with a focus on Circular water-energy-nutrient systems

D8.2 – Report on the project website, corporate identity, and communication toolkit

Timeline of activities: M1-M6

Work Package leader: PROTON

V1.0

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Abstract	This document provides an overview of communication and dissemination building blocks including, but not limited to the structure and contents of the PrAectiCe project’s corporate identity, website, and communication toolkit.
Keywords	Brand Identity, Website, Communication, Dissemination

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PROJECT FUNDED BY THE EUROPEAN COMMISSION		
NATURE OF THE DELIVERABLE		R*
DISSEMINATION LEVEL		
PU	Public, fully open, e.g., web (Deliverables flagged as public will be automatically published in CORDIS project's page)	PU
SEN	Sensitive, limited under the conditions of the Grant Agreement	
CLASSIFIED R-UE/ EU-R	EU RESTRICTED under the Commission Decision No2015/ 444	
CLASSIFIED C-UE/ EU-C	EU CONFIDENTIAL under the Commission Decision No2015/ 444	
CLASSIFIED S-UE/ EU-S	EU SECRET under the Commission Decision No2015/ 444	

* **R:** Document report (excluding the periodic and final reports)

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

The primary dissemination objective of the PrAectiCe project is to ensure that all results and project outputs are made available to key stakeholders. The PrAectiCe approach to dissemination will be inclusive and participatory, leveraging the expertise of the partners and encouraging discussion with stakeholders and related projects. The project partners will be involved in the dissemination activities from planning to implementation. As PrAectiCe places key stakeholders at its centre, engaging various stakeholders is essential for the project's success. Therefore, well-planned and executed dissemination efforts will ensure that targeted stakeholders become engaged. Digital and social channels will have a central role to play in the PrAectiCe dissemination strategy, as they provide extensive opportunities for PrAectiCe to inform, engage and promote the take-up of the PrAectiCe results, all the while building and strengthening relationships with target audiences. Key performance indicators – numerical targets that measure how well the project achieves its communication and dissemination goals – have been laid out in the Description of Action (DoA) for the website and selected social media channels. As the project develops, a detailed time plan for dissemination activities using these channels will be developed to ensure strategic and effective actions throughout the project and beyond (which will be described in detail in D8.1 Dissemination and Communication Strategy and Plan).

From month 1 to month 6 PrAectiCe has invested a significant effort to design and implement the Dissemination and Communication building blocks to ensure a jump start of the project's awareness, facilitate the ecosystem engagement, and offer all partners the essential communication assets to promote PrAectiCe project across their ecosystems. Dissemination activities have a central role during the project lifetime to foster widespread awareness of the project and strengthen cooperation and exchange between European and African agroecology research communities and farming communities in Africa. Dedicated dissemination and communication channels have been established for all stakeholders and the general audience, and a comprehensive plan of target activities has been elaborated. The dissemination and communication channels aim to inform all stakeholders, the scientific community, the farming communities in Africa, and the public about the project activities and results. This document describes in detail the project branding toolkit and website, which went online on the 20th of December, 2022. The PrAectiCe Brand Identity Toolkit includes a logo and a unique format for sharing templates for presentations, publications, leaflets, reports, posters, and guidelines specifications. The PrAectiCe project website is one of the most important information channels for the public to become aware of PrAectiCe's goals and tools. It will be continuously updated and enriched throughout the project's duration. The Deliverable is organised into three main Sections.

- Brand Identity
- Communication Toolkit
- Online Communication

The document is intended to be a reference point for all project partners, reviewers, and advisors. Its outcomes will influence several other project actions and deliverables and shape and influence other deliverables.

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ABBREVIATIONS

AU	African Union
CMS	Content Management System
DoA	Description of the Action
EU	European Union
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
QR	Quick Response
SSL	Secure Socket Layer
URL	Uniform Resource Locator
WP	Work Package

1 INTRODUCTION: COMMUNICATION AND DISSEMINATION FOUNDATIONS

The PrAEctiCe brand strategy represents the foundation of all dissemination and communication activities as it underpins all aspects of the PrAEctiCe brand and transmits the PrAEctiCe brand values and essence. This deliverable D8.2 provides evidence of advances towards achieving project objectives by defining the strategy of developing and implementing a consistent brand for the PrAEctiCe project.

A basic definition of "a brand" is the array of perceptions and associations that the subject of the branding provokes in others. It is rarely left to chance and is primarily a carefully crafted and systematically implemented series of messages and actions that invest meaning into the product/service/concept's name and identity. This is achieved in two phases: definition and agreement, and the implementation plan to achieve the defined targets. This document will describe the development of the PrAEctiCe brand strategy, from defining each key element of the Brand to including, as an Annex, the first complete booklet of Brand Guidelines for PrAEctiCe. The document is intended to be a reference point for all project partners, reviewers, and advisors. Its outcomes will influence many other project actions and WP8 deliverables.

Task 8.2 oversees establishing adequate interaction channels with different target audiences and developing the relevant content and communication materials. It is responsible for the: design of the PrAEctiCe visual identity, brand guidelines and basic promotional toolkit design and updating the project website; establishing and animating the project's social media (LinkedIn, Twitter, Facebook and YouTube) and the production of promotional and educational materials (such as roll-up, posters, flyers) to be used and distributed at events, editing and publishing of quarterly newsletters.

2 PRAECTICE BRAND IDENTITY

The recognition and perception of a brand are highly influenced by its visual presentation. A project's visual identity is the overall look of its communications. Effective visual brand identity is achieved by constantly using visual elements, such as fonts, colours, and graphic elements, to create distinction. From time to time, the brand may be used in different executions, but the visual language is the same. This uniformity creates familiarity and, with it, admiration.

2.1 LOGO

PrAECTiCe's logo builds on and reflects the core content of the project. It is based on the theme of harmonious workings of research and water to produce a successful plant. The circle device communicates that infinite information can be collected and used to sustain the plant. The fonts are clear and friendly, balanced proportionately with the typeface. The colours chosen are to suggest sustainability and freshness.

The highlight of the brand identity is the sustainable plant. It embodies the idea of moving forward, mentorship and togetherness. The primary logo has variations and formats to allow readability and usability (*Figure 1* and *Figure 2*). For the most part, the logo will have the monogram (*Figure 3*) and wordmark (*Figure 4*) combined, but there are some instances when the monogram can be used separately from the wordmark. Still, the wordmark exceptions usually occur with giveaway merchandise and sometimes the website. The full-colour logo will always be used as a preference.

The logo should always include an isolation area (*Figure 5*).

FIGURE 1: FULL-COLOUR LOGO

FIGURE 2: BLACK AND WHITE LOGO

FIGURE 3: MONOGRAM

FIGURE 4: WORDMARK

FIGURE 5: ISOLATION AREA

2.2 COLOURS

PrAEctiCe colours are simple; they represent the unity of water, air, and organics. PrAEctiCe's primary colours (Figure 6) are blue, green, turquoise, and grey.

Primary Colours

FIGURE 6: PRIMARY BRAND COLOURS

2.3 TYPOGRAPHY

PrAECTiCe brand uses Google Fonts’ open-source font family Nunito for headlines and the Ubuntu font family as body copy. The usage of other versions of the font is allowed. This applies to the website, presentations, and all promotional materials. For projected outside design department’s deliverables, the system font Calibri (Light, Regular and Bold) versions should be used instead to avoid missing font issues, as those documents will likely be mainly edited outside design departments. It could also be used for presentations if the two main brand fonts are missing.

The primary font families chosen are Nunito (Sans Serif typeface superfamily), used for the wordmark, complimented with “Ubuntu” (OpenType-based family typeface), used for text throughout designs and Calibri.

All three fonts suit print, screen, web, and titling usage. The Nunito (*Figure 7*) font is bold and confident, and Ubuntu (*Figure 8*) is modern and humanistic. The two primary fonts combined in print and online communication lend themselves to readability and a clear, trusting, and impactful brand. Calibri (*Figure 9*) is used exclusively for our online presentations and documents, being a default font in most operative systems, to maximise compatibility.

Our fonts were explicitly selected because they have ties with modern-urban. Both fonts are constructed with smooth curves and true italics, giving the text an unexpectedly sophisticated industrial look and a friendly approachability in all weights.

FIGURE 7: PRIMARY FONT, NUNITO

FIGURE 8: SECONDARY FONT, UBUNTU

FIGURE 9: PRESENTATION FONT, CALIBRI

Accessibility: The recommended minimum font size for core content text is size 10. Considering the needs of people with sight problems and behavioural patterns in reading text online, web text will be between 12 and 14 points. The body copy should be left-aligned.

2.4 BRAND GUIDE

A detailed brand guideline has been designed by Prototipi and made available to all the partners on the cloud repository (Appendix A).

2.5 EUROPEAN COMMISSION RECOGNITION

All the Dissemination and Communication materials are to acknowledge that the EC funds the project. The elements of the EU recognition can be arranged in different positions and follows the EU guidelines.

FIGURE 10: EU RECOGNITION ELEMENTS

3 PRAECTICE COMMUNICATION TOOL KIT

3.1 TEMPLATES

All PrAectiCe outputs will benefit from the corporate design to harmonise the materials' visuals and give the reader a fast-visual recognition that the material is part of PrAectiCe. Standardised templates for communication and dissemination and project reporting purposes have been created. They have been made available on the dedicated online project's repository, accessible to all the partners. These include:

- PowerPoint presentation template (Appendix B)
- Deliverable report template (Appendix C)
- Press release template (Appendix D)

The templates incorporate the European flag, the project logo, the partners' logos, and a point of contact and suggest what information must be included in the specific document.

3.2 PROMOTIONAL MATERIALS

- **Bookmark.** Prototipi printed 900 full-colour, two-sided bookmarks and distributed a small supply to each partner during the Consortium meeting in Kisumu, Kenya. The PrAectiCe bookmark is a compact and convenient promotional item for distribution by partners during relevant events to interested parties. The bookmark supplies a brief overview of the project objective and consortium members and a QR code to drive viewers to the PrAectiCe project website. The bookmark is also uploaded on the promotional materials dedicated area of the website for download (in pdf format).

FIGURE 11: BOOKMARK, FRONT

FIGURE 12: BOOKMARK, BACK

- **PrAectiCe Project Slide Deck.** The PrAectiCe Project Slide Deck (Appendix E) facilitates the partners' dissemination at events and presentations. Prototipi prepared an introductory Project

presentation which can be customised based on the partner's needs, the type of events/presentation and the target audience. It is also uploaded on the Promotional dedicated area of the website for download (in pdf format).

- **Pull-Up Banner.** Prototipi printed one single-sided, full-colour, 2-meter banner with the mechanism and carry bag for the Living Lab visit in Kisumu, Kenya; after that, it was handed over to one of the partners for use at relevant events. The pull-up banner supplies a brief overview of the project objective and consortium members; The pull-up banner is uploaded on the dedicated area of the PrAectiCe project website. It can be used for promoting the brand without demanding additional input. It is available on the website for download (in pdf format). The PrAectiCe pull-up banner, or retractable banner, can be used as an exhibition banner to assist in creating awareness by being a constant reminder and the QR code to drive viewers to the website.

FIGURE 13: ROLL-UP BANNER

- **Poster.** The PrAectiCe poster is a visual medium intended to be informative and capture the attention of a moving audience at various relevant institution notice boards. This A4 size poster introduces the project with a short description and directs the audience to the website using a QR code. The poster is uploaded on the dedicated area of the website for download (in pdf format). Prototipi printed 75 full-colour A4 posters and distributed a supply to the project partners during the Living Lab visit in Kisumu, Kenya.

FIGURE 14: A4 POSTER

All the promotional materials are available in print file format on the shared drive for the partners and downloadable from the website in low resolution for dissemination on the website.

4 PRAECTICE ONLINE COMMUNICATION

4.1 PRAECTICE WEBSITE

4.1.1 Website Objectives

The PrAECTiCe website (www.praactice.eu), published online in December 2022 (M2), is the nucleus of the project's online communications. The project website caters for different audiences who can navigate easily to dedicated website sections. The audience includes:

- African farmers and multipliers (farmers' associations, NGOs focused on agriculture development in Africa etc.)
- academic and industry researchers
- agroecology innovators
- policymakers (in the EU and Africa)
- project partners
- citizens

The website is a powerful communication tool and a key engagement element for the PrAECTiCe project. The website provides well-presented non-confidential project information, including:

- project concept and methodology
- partners information
- core objectives
- co-creation activities
- living labs
- training materials
- decision support tools
- results
- events, news
- public deliverables and scientific publications
- links to relevant EU projects and initiatives

Prototipi has built the PrAECTiCE website and is maintaining it regularly. The website content required is continuously developed as the project progresses. This involves writing, editing and proofreading written content for each page. Material is gathered from all partners to ensure a stream of content.

4.1.2 Website Structure

Given the broad range of audiences for the site, each with a different level of knowledge and expertise, the navigation allows that audience to access the section of the site relevant to them easily. PrAECTiCe has kept the website's structure with the fewest clicks to get to relevant content. This approach is also rewarding concerning Search Engine ranking results while ensuring accessibility and user-friendliness.

FIGURE 15: WEBSITE STRUCTURE

4.1.3 Full Responsive Website

The PrAectiCe project website is a fully responsive website that contains extensive and relevant information on the PrAectiCe project's vision and objectives with easy access and a user-friendly interface to showcase information and any public material generated within the project, as well as materials gathered via the various work packages activities about ongoing projects and relevant initiatives. Web design experts within the project consortium conceived its design and structure to promote the outcomes to the appropriate target groups. The website is fully mobile-responsive (Figure 16), and all pages have been reformatted to reproduce what visitors experience on desktop viewing. Website updates have been continuously and promptly implemented and will remain to be updated throughout the lifespan of the PrAectiCe Project.

FIGURE 16: MOBILE-RESPONSIVE

As shown in *Figure 17*, the project website's home page has evolved into a clear and clean communication interface that is easily navigable and contains all relevant project-related public information.

FIGURE 17: PRAECTICE WEBSITE HOMEPAGE

The PrAectiCe website is structured into the following sections:

○ **About**

This section (*Figure 18*) contains the vision and objectives, motivation, concept, and methodology of the PrAectiCe project. To present it in a user-friendly way, subsections have been created.

- *Vision & Objectives:* This page explains how PrAectiCe intends to build bridges, create opportunities, empower smallholder farmers, and ensure sustainability. The narrative has been kept short and relevant, breaking text with the introduction of icons designed especially for the PrAectiCe Brand.
- *The Consortium:* This page introduces the Partners working together on the PrAectiCe project and links to their websites.

FIGURE 18: PRAECTICE WEBSITE ABOUT PAGE

○ **Co-Creation Activities**

This page was created to further elaborate on the activities that will be developed with the project's stakeholders to yield the best possible outcome. The nature of these activities contributes to the project's core objectives, thus requiring a dedicated page to explain the nature to the audience thoroughly.

○ **Training**

The project's success requires stakeholders to uptake the information and outputs provided by the research. Training of stakeholders is a crucial element in ensuring fruitful outcomes. The dedicated training page on the PrAectiCe project website explains how training programs will be implemented.

○ **Decision Support Tool**

Audiences unfamiliar with a Decision Support Tool can find a detailed description of the technology and the purpose of the PrAectiCe project.

○ **Living Labs**

As it should be noticed, only some of the viewers of the PrAectiCe website fully understand what Living Labs are; it is essential to have a page that explains each and refers the viewer to find out more information on the matter.

○ **Events**

Future events related to the project, such as meetings, workshops, or conferences or those that could be interesting due to their relationship with the project topic, will also be gathered under this section. Past events have also been included so that website visitors can find relevant information.

○ **Library**

PrAectiCe also has a Library Section (*Figure 19*) with all the dissemination materials available for download. To have the information categorised, subsections are included.

- *Policy briefs*: A list of policy documents for relevant entities at the country and national level in East Africa will be kept here. As well as recommendations for applicable EU policies and priorities.
- *Relevant initiatives*: This section acts as a base for specific initiatives that include closely related projects and a selection of smaller milestones that work together to progress towards high-level visions and objectives.
- *Scientific Publications*: All scientific publications related to the project will be gathered under this subsection. Full paper and abstract download possibilities will also be set up when available.
- *Deliverables*: Present the list of public deliverables, which will be uploaded and made available once submitted.
- *Promotional Material*: leaflets, brochures, logos and all the documents aimed to construct the corporative image of the project will be gathered under this subsection.

FIGURE 19: PRACTICE WEBSITE LIBRARY

○ **What's New**

This section covers subsections including *news, press releases and press clippings, newsletters, and videos* (*Figure 20*) related to the project. It will often be updated with new information to inform the audience of the project's progress. Concerning the news: meeting execution, milestones achieved, and other relevant information about the ongoing project will be included here. Most news entries are spread through PrAectiCe social media channels to increase visibility and promotion. It also features the press releases issued by the project and collects the related media coverage. The PrAectiCe website Social Media link and a “Subscribe to our Newsletter” option have been visually included.

FIGURE 20: PRACTICE WHAT'S THE NEWS PAGE

○ Contact Us

On this page, PrAectiCe reinforces the option to follow and connect with PrAectiCe on social media from the website and quickly fills out the “send us a message” form.

FIGURE 21: CONTACT US PAGE WITH RECAPTCHV3 ACTIVE

4.1.4 Content Management System

The PrAectiCe website was built using the WordPress Content Management System (CMS). WordPress is a content management system (CMS for short). It's a robust tool for creating and managing your website. WordPress controls 60% of the CMS market and powers 34% of all websites worldwide. Numbers like this are simply staggering. Big-name sites like TED, TechCrunch, UPS, and CNN all use

WordPress. Each month roughly 70 million new posts are published on WordPress. It's safe to say that a WordPress platform is not only popular but reliable as well. Below are a few reasons the WordPress Platform has been chosen for the PrAECTiCe website.

- WordPress has excellent support as it is used by many worldwide; countless guides, tutorials, and resources can be found online.
- WordPress makes SEO easy by having built-in tools that tell you how SEO-friendly your content is.
- WordPress is flexible and can be as in-depth, complex, or simple as you want.
- WordPress is a safe and secure platform. It's also easy to enable an SSL certificate for your WordPress site.
- Slow websites are useless. WordPress knows this, so it has specific features and elements that you can take advantage of that will speed up your website.

Since its inception, PrAECTiCe has been working on supporting the traffic to the website through:

- SEO (Search Engine Optimization): the traffic of visits to the project's website will increase progressively throughout the project, thanks to implementing strategies oriented to organic traffic, always considering the keywords identified.
- Link building: It will create synergies between the project's website and the partners' websites, as well as with other relevant agents of the sector (stakeholders), encouraging the exchange of links.

4.1.5 Secure Sockets Layer

Without SSL, PrAECTiCe site visitors and customers are at higher risk of having their data stolen. Our site security is also at risk without encryption. SSL protects the PrAECTiCe website from phishing scams, data breaches, and other threats. Ultimately, it builds a secure environment for both visitors and site owners.

Active SSL on any site can be seen with HTTPS included on the URL of the site.

FIGURE 22: URL INDICATING SITE IS SECURE

4.1.6 Website Privacy Policy and Legal Notice

The Privacy Policy (Figure 24) of the PrAectiCe website and Legal Notice (Figure 23) have dedicated pages and can be accessed on all pages at the bottom left-hand corner of the website. It explains the reason for processing users' data, details how we collect, handle and ensure the protection of all personal data provided, how that information is used and what rights users have concerning their personal data by the General Data Protection Regulation. A cookie acceptance pop-up is also incorporated into the website. Cookies are small text files saved on your computer, mobile phone or tablet. They allow the website to remember user actions and preferences (such as login, language, font size and other display preferences) so that users do not have to re-enter them whenever they return. Users can control and delete cookies as they wish.

FIGURE 23: TERMS & CONDITIONS: LEGAL NOTICE

FIGURE 24: PRIVACY POLICY

4.1.7 Website measuring results

Matomo Analytics¹ is used to track the number of visits and analyse trends in visitor behaviours to the project's website. PrAectiCe chose to use Matomo analytics for several reasons: a) data ownership, Matomo does not use data for marketing activities, b) Matomo was designed with visitors' privacy in mind, and it is configured to follow the GDPR requirements, c) Matomo is free and open-source e) Matomo Cloud's secure servers are based in Germany – therefore adhering to the GDPR. This monitoring will be carried out throughout the project. Valuable insights may be obtained, including how long visitors remain on the website, how many pages the website visitors view, and which content is most popular. The content and structure of the website may then be tailored to satisfy the interests of the website visitors, thus attracting additional traffic. Search engine optimisation is a crucial element in promoting traffic to a website. The website needs to be updated regularly with content including key tag words, which allow search engines to prioritise websites based on the search words users select.

1 <https://matomo.org/>

FIGURE 25: PRACTICE MATOMO ANALYTICS

At the time of writing, the website has already counted **1123 visits** (Figure 26); the average time spent on the website is **5 Minutes and 7 seconds**, an excellent result indicating the richness and relevance of the website for online visitors.

FIGURE 26: WEBSITE VISITS

The Web Traffic Sources metric measures which traffic sources drive website visitors. In this project, the top ten countries (Figure 27) traffic origin is noted in Figure 28.

FIGURE 27: TOP 10 COUNTRIES' WEBSITE VISITS

FIGURE 28: WEBSITE TRAFFIC ORIGIN AND TRANSITION

4.2 NEWSFLASH AND NEWSLETTER

- **Newsflash**
Short newsflashes are sent out regularly to promote highlights and announcements of interest from an ecosystem-wide perspective. The first newsflash was sent out in December 2022 and is available on the PrAectiCe website.
- **Newsletter**
An e-Newsletter is to be edited by the PrAectiCE every quarter to provide regular updates on

project results, partner news and upcoming events. As such, a typical project e-newsletter contains highlights (primary outcomes, links, contacts, and dissemination activities), the most important news, announcements, and a schedule of the major upcoming events. Mailings with invitations to relevant workshops and webinars, consultations and other information that cannot wait for the newsletter publication or cannot appear only in the newsletter will be sent out regularly to the same database used for the newsletter. Project partners provide information for the e-Newsletter and ensure accurate content. PrAectiCe has created a profile on Mailerlite, using it as its mail client platform. Mailerlite Servers are based in the EU, guaranteeing full adherence to GDPR. It provides real-time reporting on the number of subscribers, bounced rate, and opening and clicks rate of each PrAectiCe e-Newsletter. A mailing list has been created, based on subscription, allowing sharing of the e-newsletter via mass mailing and informing interested users about project news, achievements, and planning of events. A registration functionality enabling interested visitors to subscribe to the newsletter has been available on the PrAectiCe website since January 2023. All these actions will be ensured to comply with the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) requirements. The newsletter's design has been developed (*Figure 29*), and it provides a clear branding and content template, flexible enough for communication needs. The newsletter's first issue was published on 31 March 2023 and reached 35 current subscribers. Newsletters are uploaded on the website.

FIGURE 29: PRACTICE NEWSLETTER

4.3 SOCIAL MEDIA

PrAectiCe seeks to engage a broad audience using social media networks. Once the PrAectiCe design was consolidated, social media tools such as Twitter (*Figure 31*), Facebook (*Figure 32*), and LinkedIn (*Figure 30*) were launched in November 2022. This has contributed to ensuring active and dynamic visibility of the start of the project, its developments, and the establishment of contacts and links with other projects and individuals. Posts are shared to support the news flow, and content is added continuously. At the time of writing, the Twitter (<https://twitter.com/PrAectiCe>) account already has 129 followers, the LinkedIn (<https://www.linkedin.com/company/practice/>) page has 193 followers, and the Facebook (<https://www.facebook.com/PrAectiCe>) page has 39 Followers. The YouTube account will be opened after the first video is released. We expect to exceed the KPIs for social media accounts.

FIGURE 30: PRACTICE LINKEDIN PROFILE

FIGURE 31: PRACTICE TWITTER PROFILE

FIGURE 32: PRACTICE FACEBOOK PAGE

5 CONCLUSION AND NEXT STEPS

This deliverable has outlined the approaches and activities that have been taken for three of the core components of the communication and dissemination actions for the PrAECTiCe project:

- Brand
- Communication Tools
- Website, Newsletter, and social media

It has outlined the core thinking and critical principles behind all three and described how this thinking influenced the planned implementation of each component. It has been established that the approach to be taken in each of the three will be, by necessity, dynamic and will be updated and developed throughout the lifetime of the PrAECTiCe project.

Deliverable D8.1 Dissemination & Stakeholder Engagement Strategy (M6) will go into more detail about the dissemination and communication strategy. Task 8.2 will ensure the appropriate application of the brand guidelines and supports the partners in the material adaptation according to the needs and development of new materials as the project evolves. The website will be continuously updated, ensuring all partners across all communication apply the appropriate EU recognition.

APPENDIX A

2022 - 2026 PrAectiCe

3

The Brand

Why use these Guidelines?

We are very proud of our brand PrAectiCe, and would like to see our brand expressed correctly throughout all styles of communication; electronic and printed visual media.

From time to time, we may use the brand in different executions but the visual language is the same. This uniformity creates familiarity, and with it, admiration.

01

BRAND GUIDELINE

2022 - 2026 PrAectiCe

4

01. The Brand

Our Purpose

Our Foundational Principle

The vision of PrAectiCe is to provide a novel Agro-Ecology indicator set for East Africa, aimed at helping smallholder farmers in their agro-ecological transition.

BRAND GUIDELINE

2022 - 2026 PrAectiCe

5

The Logo

Complete Branding Guidelines next project.

01. FINAL LOGO
02. CLEARSPACE

03. BACKGROUNDS
04. DO NOT

The highlight of the logo is the sustainable plant.

It embodies the idea of moving forward, mentorship and togetherness.

It symbolizes the harmonious workings of research and water to produce a successful plant. The circle device communicates that there is infinite information that can be collected and used to sustain the plant.

The colours chosen are to suggest sustainability and freshness. The fonts are clear and friendly and balanced proportionately with the typeface.

02

BRAND GUIDELINE

2022 - 2026 PrAectiCe

6

01. The Logo

Final Logo

Complete Branding Guidelines next project.

The main logo is also provided in the variations depicted here below, to allow readability or for black and white printing purposes. The full colour logo should always be used as a preference.

Full Colour

Monogram

Wordmark

Monogram and Wordmark

Our Monogram can be used on its own under special circumstances, eg. social media avatars. Our wordmark can never be used alone and should always be combined with our monogram.

BRAND GUIDELINE

PrAectiCe

2022 - 2026 PrAectiCe

7

01. The Logo

Clear Space

Isolation Area

Our logo should always stand steadfast and by encouraging clear space surrounding our logo we will be able to achieve this by following the guidance.

BRAND GUIDELINE

PrAectiCe

2022 - 2026 PrAectiCe

8

01. The Logo

Backgrounds

Placement of image

We're proud of our logo, so readability is essential. We don't want to restrict you on our logo position placement on a page, however, we do feel that where it is the place needs to serve a purpose and be clear and visible. Image selection is very important and too much detail will allow our logo to get lost on the page. We do suggest on an image to use a one colour logo instead of a full colour logo.

BRAND GUIDELINE

BRAND GUIDELINE

01. The Logo

2022 - 2026 PrAectiCe

9

Do Not

Respect the brand

We love our logo as is, and no matter how you feel you can make it better please don't. We don't want to see our logo colour changed. We don't want to see our wordmark font changed. There is only one variation of our logo and this is it.

PrAectiCe

PrAectiCe

PrAectiCe

BRAND GUIDELINE

02. The Colours

2022 - 2026 PrAectiCe

10

The Colours

Why these colours?

Our colours are simple, they represent the unity of water, air and organics.

Our colours should never be replaced or substituted as its the pride of our brand.

03

BRAND GUIDELINE

01. The Colours

2022 - 2026 PrAectiCe

11

Primary Colours

cmyk : 92 / 65 / 0 / 0
 pantone : 7455
 rgb : R18 G98 B175
 # 1262af

cmyk : 47 / 0 / 18 / 0
 pantone : 318
 rgb : R129 G208 B212
 # 81d0d4

cmyk : 30 / 0 / 80 / 0
 pantone : 374
 rgb : R188 G216 B95
 # bcd85f

cmyk : 8 / 5 / 8 / 0
 pantone : 7541
 rgb : R232 G232 B228
 # e8e8e4

BRAND GUIDELINE

01. The Colours

2022 - 2026 PrAectiCe

12

How the colours blend

How our colours work together?

There is no specific ratio to the balance of our colours. This is just an example of how our colours look together to create a well-balanced tone of colours.

2022 - 2026 PrAectiCe

13

The Typography

Why these fonts?

PrAectiCe brand uses Google Fonts' open source font family Nunito for headlines and Ubuntu font family as body copy.

The usage of other versions of the font is allowed. This applies to the website, presentations and all promotional materials.

For project's deliverables, the system font Calibri (Light, Regular and Bold versions) should be used instead, to avoid missing font issues, as those documents are likely to be mainly edited outside design departments. It could be used also for presentations in case the two main brand fonts are missing.

04

BRAND GUIDELINE

2022 - 2026 PrAectiCe

14

01. The Typography

Primary Font

About Nunito

Nunito is PrAectiCe's core typeface, used for the PrAectiCe wordmark, headlines and throughout the designs. Nunito is a well balanced sans serif typeface superfamily, approachability in all weights.

Designed by Vernon Adams, Cyreal, Jacques Le Bailly

<https://fonts.google.com/specimen/Nunito?query=nuni>

Light	<i>Light Italic</i>
Medium	<i>Medium Italic</i>
Bold	<i>Bold Italic</i>
Black	<i>Black Italic</i>

Aa

ABCDEFGHIJKLMNOPQRSTUVWXYZ
abcdefghijklmnopqrstuvwxyz
012345678910!@#%&

BRAND GUIDELINE

BRAND GUIDELINE

01. The Typography 2022 - 2026 PrAectiCe

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Secondary Font

About Ubuntu

Ubuntu is PrAectiCe's secondary typeface, used for the text throughout the designs. Ubuntu is an OpenType-based font family, designed to be a modern, humanist-style typeface.

Designed by Dalton Maag

<https://fonts.google.com/specimen/Ubuntu?query=ubuntu>

Bb

Light *Light Italic*

Regular *Regular Italic*

Medium *Medium Italic*

Black *Black Italic*

ABCDEFGHIJKLMNOPQRSTUVWXYZ
abcdefghijklmnopqrstuvwxyz
012345678910!@#\$\$%&

BRAND GUIDELINE

01. The Typography 2022 - 2026 PrAectiCe

16

Presentation Font

About Calibri

Calibri is a modern sans serif family with subtle roundings on stems and corners. It features real italics, small caps, and multiple numeral sets. Its proportions allow high impact in tightly set lines of big and small text alike. Calibri's many curves and the new rasteriser team up in bigger sizes to reveal a warm and soft character.

Luc(as) de Groot (Standard Latin, Cyrillic, Greek, and Hebrew), Mamoun Sakkal (Arabic), Armenian and Georgian (Ruben Tatumian)

Cc

Light

Regular *Regular Italic*

Medium *Bold Italic*

ABCDEFGHIJKLMNOPQRSTUVWXYZ
abcdefghijklmnopqrstuvwxyz
012345678910!@#\$\$%&

2022 - 2026 PrAectiCe

17

The EC Recognition

Acknowledgment

All the EC funded projects should clearly show the acknowledgement to the EC fund in all Dissemination & Communication materials (e.g. flyers, posters, roll-ups, brochures, videos, webiste, etc).

05

BRAND GUIDELINE

2022 - 2026 PrAectiCe

18

01. The EU Recognition

EU Recognition

Full EU logo & acknowledgement

Below there are some examples of the elements to show in different positions.

The EU logo and recognition may not be altered in any way and should follow the strict EU guidelines, which can be accessed here: https://ec.europa.eu/regional_policy/en/information/logos_downloadcenter/

Funded by the European Union

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BRAND GUIDELINE

APPENDIX B

PRACTICE.EU

Click to add title

Presented by: XXX | Organisation
Date

Funded by the European Union

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PRACTICE.EU

PrAECTiCe will provide a novel Agroecology indicator set for East Africa, aimed at helping smallholder farmers in their agroecological transition.

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2022-2026 PRACTICE

PRAECTICE.EU

01

Click to add title

Click to edit sub title

2022-2026 PRAECTICE

PRAECTICE.EU

Click to add title

Click here to insert subheading

Title	Description	Title	Description	Title
Title	Description	Title	Description	Title

2022-2026 PRAECTICE

Insert image or leave plain colour

Click to add title

Click here to insert subheading

Click to add text

Funded by the European Union

2022-2026 PRACTICE

Click to add title

Click here to insert subheading

Funded by the European Union

2022-2026 PRACTICE

The graphic features a central image of a green field with a blue grid and binary code overlay. On the left, the PrAectiCe logo and 'PrAectiCe' text are repeated. Below the logo is the website 'PRACTICE.EU'. At the bottom left is the 'Funded by the European Union' logo. On the right, the text 'Thank you' is written in a large, blue, italicized font. Below this are three social media icons (Twitter, LinkedIn, Facebook) with their respective URLs: twitter.com/PrAectiCe, www.linkedin.com/company/praectice/, and <https://www.facebook.com/PrAectiCe>. At the bottom right, the text '2022-2026 PRACTICE' is displayed.

APPENDIX C

Deliverable heading goes here

Sub-heading goes here

Revision Version: 01

Work package	WP.00000
Task	Task 00000
Due date	00/00/0000
Deliverable date	00/00/0000
Deliverable lead	Name partner
Version	0.X
00000	Name 000000 (Partner 1)
000000	Name 000000 (Partner 1)
Abstract	000000000
Keywords	

Document Revision History

VERSION	DATE	DESCRIPTION OF CHANGE	LIST OF CONTRIBUTORS

D8.2 - Deliverable-Title (V-xx)

Providing evidence on the ecological indicator set for Africa, aimed at helping small farmers to their ecological transition

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Disclaimer

The information, documentation and figures available in this deliverable are written by the PrAectiCe project's consortium under EC grant agreement 00000, and do not necessarily reflect the views of the European Commission.

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PROJECT CO-FUNDED BY THE EUROPEAN COMMISSION	
NATURE OF THE DELIVERABLE	TO SPECIFY R, DEM, DEC, DATA, DMP, ETHICS, SECURITY, OTHER*
DISSEMINATION LEVEL	
PU	Public, fully open, e.g. web (Deliverables flagged as public will be automatically published in CORDIS project's page)
SEN	Sensitive, limited under the conditions of the Grant Agreement
CLASSIFIED R-UE/ EU-R	EU RESTRICTED under the Commission Decision No2015/ 444
CLASSIFIED C-UE/ EU-C	EU CONFIDENTIAL under the Commission Decision No2015/ 444
CLASSIFIED S-UE/ EU-S	EU SECRET under the Commission Decision No2015/ 444

* R: Document, report, (excluding the periodic and final reports)
 DEM: Demonstration, pilot, prototype, pilot, designs
 DEC: Webinars, webinars, press & media actions, videos, etc.
 DATA: Data sets, metadata, etc.
 DMP: Data management plan
 ETHICS: Deliverables related to ethics issues
 SECURITY: Deliverables related to security issues
 OTHER: Software, technical diagram, algorithms, models, etc.

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D8.2: Deliverable Title (V x.x)

Providing a novel Agro-Ecology initiative and for Africa, aimed at helping small farmers in their Agro-Ecological transition

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

About The Executive Summary:

Summaries are useful for people who have neither the time nor the inclination to read a lengthy document but who want to scan the primary points quickly and then decide whether they need to read the entire version.

A summary should be short enough to be economical and long enough to be clear and comprehensive. Don't sacrifice meaning for brevity. A short, confusing summary will take more of a busy executive's time than a somewhat longer but clear one.

It should stand alone (hence do not refer to section numbers or WPs).

- It focuses on results (findings, conclusions, and recommendations).
- It typically provides some motivation for why the problem is interesting.
- It typically mentions the research methodology.
- It does NOT need to provide a section-by-section summary.

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D8.2: Deliverable Title (V x.x)

Providing a novel Agro-Ecology initiative and for Africa, aimed at helping small farmers in their Agro-Ecological transition

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D8.2: Deliverable Title (V x.x)

Providing a novel Agro-Ecology initiative and for Africa, aimed at helping small farmers in their Agro-Ecological transition

LIST OF FIGURES

FIGURE 1: THIS FIGURE IS TAKEN FROM XXX.....

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D8.2: Deliverable Title (V x.x)

Providing a novel Agro-Ecology initiative and for Africa, aimed at helping small farmers in their Agro-Ecological transition

LIST OF TABLES

TABLE 1 : CAPTION FOR THE TABLE.....

TABLE 2 : CAPTION FOR THE AGENDA TABLE.....

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Del.: Deliverable Title (V x.x)

PrAectiCe

Abbreviations

IP Internet Protocol

TCP Transmission Control Protocol

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Del.: Deliverable Title (V x.x)

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1 SECTION: ABOUT TEXT AND TITLES

GUIDANCE:

Deliverables should not refer to project internal matters such as WPs.

1.1 FIRST SUBSECTION

Body text

- First level bullet list
 - Second level bullet list
 - Third level bullet list...

First level numbered list

- Second level numbered list
 - Third level numbered list...

1.1.1.1 Second subsection

1.1.2 Sub-subsection

1.1.2.1 Sub-sub-subsection

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Del.: Deliverable Title (V x.x)

PrAectiCe

2 SECTION: ABOUT FIGURES, TABLES AND REFERENCES

2.1 ABOUT FIGURES

About figures please remember to:

- Center them
- Put figure caption (easier to then cross-reference to them)
- Caption font size should be 8 pt italic and UPPERCASE
- Caption should be centered as well

If the picture is taken from some other sources this should be stated

▲ Illustration of Home Networking with HPNA 3.0 Coax
FIGURE 2. THIS FIGURE IS TAKEN FROM XXX

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Del.: Deliverable Title (V x.x)

PrAectiCe

ABOUT TABLES

About tables remember to:

- Center them
- Put a Table caption (easier to then cross-reference to them)
- Caption font size should be 8 pt italic and uppercase
- Caption should be centered as well

If the Table is taken from some other sources this should be stated

Hereby a table example:

TABLE 2. CAPTION FOR THE TABLE

Column 1	Column 2	Column 3
Content cell	Content cell	Content cell
Content cell	Content cell	Content cell

2.1.1 Agenda Tables

Hereby an agenda table example:

TABLE 2. CAPTION FOR THE AGENDA TABLE

Start time	Planned duration	Items description	Presenter
XXXX	xx min	XXXXXXXXXX XXXX	XXXX XXXX
XXXX	xx min	XXXXXXXX XXXX XXXX XXXX XXXX XXXX ▲ XXXXXX XXXX XXXX XXXX	XXXX XXXX
XXXX	xx min	COFFEE BREAK / LUNCH	
XXXX	xx min	XXXXXXXX XXXX XXXX XXXX XXXX XXXX	XXXX XXXX
XXXX	xx min	XXXXXXXX XXXX XXXX XXXX XXXX XXXX ▼ XXXXXX XXXX XXXX XXXX	XXXX XXXX

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APPENDIX D

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PRESS

Joint Press Release

Date goes here

By Hochschule Karlsruhe University of Applied Sciences, Steinbeis Europa Zentrum, AquaBiotech, Prototipi, University of Gothenburg, Makerere University, Uganda Martyrs University, University of Maribor, Ministry of Agriculture and Livestock Development (moALD), RUFORUM, National Agriculture Research Organisation, Maseno University, Sustainable Agriculture Tanzania (SAT), Aquagri, AFSA Africa and Africa Agribusiness Academy

PrAectiCe: XXXXXXi

- XXXX
- XXXX
- XXXX

Body Copy

Sub-Heading
Body Copy

“Quoted Text” says Adriano Mauro, Managing Director of Prototipi Nigeria, an SME based in Lagos.

The project’s partners:

Partners

APPENDIX E

PrAectiCe

Objectives

- Identify the most promising agroecological approaches for East African farms.
- Provide evidence that circular water-energy-nutrient systems of integrated aquaculture-agriculture are among the best practices for East Africa to address climate change issues while increasing financial viability.
- Provide suggestions and help smallholder farmers in their agroecological transition.
- To provide a novel agroecology indicator set focusing on circular water-energy-nutrient systems of integrated aqua-agriculture for smallholder farmers.

How will PrAectiCe do this?

1. Co-creation activities
2. Living Labs
3. Training
4. Decision Support Tool

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Project Timeline
42 Months

Funded by the European Commission

Countries Involved in the project:
Europe: Portugal, Malta, Germany, Slovenia
Africa: Kenya, Uganda, Tanzania, Nigeria

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Co-creation activities

Placing the needs of farmers at the centre by involving them in research and the evaluation of results.

Activities with local stakeholders will be developed to yield the best possible outcome:

- co-creation workshops (on PrAectiCe's indicator framework and users' stories)
- online training courses
- on-site pieces of training in PrAectiCe's living labs
- student exchange programs
- a business event for young agricultural entrepreneurs
- online surveys with stakeholders

Living Labs

3 Living Labs

1. 3 Living Labs are action-based projects that optimise water, energy, and nutrient use in 3 different Integrated aqua-agriculture systems.
2. They will produce data for validation of the Decision Support Tool.
3. The general public and other key stakeholders will have an opportunity to visit the sites and enjoy the food grown on the farm during an open-door day organised within PrAectiCe.

Where are they located, and what will they focus on?

Living lab 1: Aquaculture and intercropping (Kisumu, Kenya)

Living lab 2: Aquaculture and hydroponics (Namulonge, Uganda)

Living lab 3: Fish-poultry integrated systems (Morogoro, Tanzania)

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Living Labs

Where are they located, and what will they focus on?

Living lab 1: Aquaculture and intercropping (Kisumu, Kenya)

In this pilot, aquaculture wastewater will be reused to irrigate intercropping systems, and aquaculture sludge will be used as fertiliser.

Living lab 2: Aquaculture and hydroponics (Namulonge, Uganda)

The aquaponics living lab will consider several combinations of fish and vegetables with varying water, energy and nutrient needs which will be piloted to optimise the water-energy-nutrient resources.

Living lab 3: Fish-poultry integrated systems (Morogoro, Tanzania)

The setup will also include vegetable production by using aquaculture sludge and poultry manure to improve soil health, and wastewater from fish ponds will be used for irrigating vegetables.

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PRAECTICE.EU

Decision Support Tool

A guiding tool focussed on data collection and practical approaches to farmers' challenging situations.

1

DST Scope: Level 1
Increase the efficiency of recognising industrial inputs, mapping out and collecting data on agroecological techniques.

2

Level 2
Substitute old practices and inputs with new farming practices, classified and recognised, and with the classification of environmental events (water usage, degradation, etc.)

3

Level 3
Redesign the agroecology system, realising simulations and predictions of socio-economic and environmental impacts of the previously examined farming practices.

Will be available in the form of 3 applications:
Mobile app for farmers, a desktop application for advisors and backend for data specialists

The 4th and 5th levels will address the consumer perspective, addressing the efficiency of the system's performance and analytics.

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Training

Why?

- Helping farmers get the support they need,
- building knowledge at a local level
- and guiding them in the transition to sustainable food and agriculture

How will PrAECTiCe do so?

- A method will be followed similar to those developed By NGOs that train agroecological practices in sustainable development.
- The farmers' representatives are taught, which then go ahead and prepare, transfer knowledge and share methods with the farmers.
- On-site training for integrated aqua-agriculture will be made available to provide practical solutions for developing agroecological practices.
- Three Living Labs in East Africa will be involved in this training process.

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